

Temporal Surveillance of Multidrug-Resistant *Salmonella* Typhi in Niger State, Nigeria: A 10-Year Phenotypic and Cross-Sectional Study (2014–2024)

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ABSTRACT

The global threat of antimicrobial-resistant *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhi (*S. Typhi*) is intensifying. Yet, long-term surveillance data from regions where it is endemic remain limited. In Nigeria, the crisis has been worsened by fragmented diagnostics and the unregulated use of antibiotics. This study investigated the temporal evolution of phenotypic resistance in *S. Typhi* across Niger State, Nigeria, over a ten-year period by integrating retrospective and prospective epidemiological data. We conducted a hybrid observational study (2014–2024) that retrospectively analyzed hospital records and performed prospective microbiological surveillance across nine communities. The isolates were confirmed by biochemical and serological tests. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing followed the CLSI guidelines. Logistic regression identified predictors of multidrug resistance (MDR). Among the 624 participants, 228 (36.5%) tested positive for *S. Typhi*. MDR was observed in 75.9% of isolates, while 5.7% met the strict MDR criteria. Resistance to amoxicillin-clavulanate, cotrimoxazole, and tetracycline reached 100%, 73.5%, and 79.5%, respectively. Levofloxacin and netilmicin retained >80% efficacy. Young adults and semi-urban residents were disproportionately affected. Hospitalization and recent antibiotic use were significant predictors of MDR ($p < 0.05$). *S. Typhi* in Niger State shows escalating resistance with narrowing treatment options. Without urgent interventions, revised empirical protocols, vaccine rollouts, and antimicrobial regulations, Nigeria risks entering a post-antibiotic era of typhoid treatment.

Keywords: *Salmonella* Typhi; antimicrobial resistance; multidrug resistance; epidemiology; Nigeria; typhoid fever

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INTRODUCTION

Typhoid fever caused by *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhi (*S. Typhi*), "continues to pose a substantial public health challenge in sub-Saharan Africa, where its persistence is largely due to inadequate water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) infrastructure (Musa et al., 2019; WHO, 2022; Crump et al., 2023). Globally, the disease affects 11–21 million people annually, leading to over 160,000 deaths (Hancuh et al., 2023; Kariuki and Onsare, 2024). However, the current estimates of the global burden may significantly underestimate the true impact (Obaro et al., 2017).

The endemicity of typhoid fever in Nigeria is well documented (Reuben et al., 2013) and is exacerbated by multidrug resistance (MDR), which complicates treatment and control. However, the longitudinal relationship between typhoid fever and MDR remains unclear. Methodological limitations in population-based studies across low- and middle-income countries often lead to the underestimation of incidence rates (Mogasale et al., 2015; Akinyemi et al., 2018; Okeke et al., 2022), highlighting the need for more comprehensive and systematic epidemiological approaches. Consequently, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) trends, especially in MDR *S. Typhi*, have not been well characterized. MDR *S. Typhi*, defined as resistance to at least three first-line antibiotics (ampicillin, chloramphenicol, and co-trimoxazole), is becoming increasingly common in Africa and Asia (Browne et al., 2018; Klemm et al., 2018). Additionally, the reduced susceptibility to fluoroquinolones and third-generation cephalosporins has made empirical treatment more complex (Marchello et al., 2020; Rasheed et al., 2020).

The emergence and persistence of MDR *S. Typhi* in Nigeria are linked to several factors including the widespread availability of antibiotics without prescriptions, limited diagnostic capacity, and fragmented AMR surveillance systems (Okeke et al., 2022; Akinyemi et al., 2022). Moreover, the lack of region-specific data impairs the design of targeted interventions. National and global health bodies have underscored the urgent need to integrate laboratory-confirmed AMR data with contextual determinants, including local health-seeking behaviors, WASH access, and

sociodemographic risk factors (WHO GLASS, 2021).

Niger State, a diverse region with rural, semi-urban, and urban populations, exemplifies the infrastructural and health-system variability observed across Nigeria. However, no comprehensive study has assessed the temporal dynamics of MDR *S. Typhi* in this state over an extended period. This knowledge gap hinders the development of locally adapted treatment guidelines and public health policies.

To address this gap, this study aimed to assess ten-year temporal trends in antimicrobial resistance among *S. Typhi* isolates in Niger State (2014–2023); perform phenotypic characterization of contemporary isolates; and identify demographic and clinical factors associated with MDR. By combining retrospective surveillance data with prospective microbiological analyses, this study provides a foundation for evidence-based antimicrobial stewardship and disease-control strategies in Nigeria.

METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This hybrid retrospective prospective observational study was conducted in Niger State, North-Central Nigeria, between January 2014 and August 2024. The study encompassed nine communities: Minna, Lapai, Bida, Suleja, Zungeru, New Bussa, Wushishi, Kontagora, and Sabon Wuse. Health facilities with operational microbiology laboratories were selected in rural, semi-urban, and urban settings.

Phase I: Retrospective Surveillance (2014–2023)

Retrospective data were extracted from the microbiology registers and electronic health records of nine hospitals and diagnostic laboratories: Federal Medical Center Bida, IBB Specialized Hospital Minna, General Hospital Lapai, Musa Inuwa Hospital Minna, General Hospital Minna, General Hospital Sabon Wuse, General Hospital Suleja, General Hospital Kontagora, and General Hospital New Bussa. Eligible cases were defined as patients with laboratory-confirmed *S. Typhi* infections verified by a culture test accompanied by compatible clinical symptoms. Only records with complete demographic data and antibiotic susceptibility profiles were included in this study. The

extracted data included age, sex, residence, diagnosis date, and antimicrobial susceptibility test (AST) results.

Phase II: Prospective Cross-Sectional Study (2023–2024)

This cross-sectional study was conducted from August 2023 to August 2024 in Niger State. The participants were selected using a multistage random sampling method to ensure representation across urban, semi-urban, and rural settings. Community health workers assisted in identifying households and individuals were approached in person. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment. A total of 624 individuals agreed to participate in the study, reflecting a range of socio-clinical profiles.

Sample Collection and Transport

Each participant provided a fresh stool sample in a sterile 40 mL specimen container. The samples were stored at 4°C and transported to the Trans-Saharan Disease Research Center Laboratory, Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University, Lapai, within 4–6 h. All samples were processed under biosafety level 2 (BSL-2) conditions.

Microbiological Isolation and Identification

Stool specimens were inoculated on Salmonella-Shigella Agar (SSA, Oxoid, UK) and Bismuth Sulfite Agar (BSA, HiMedia, India) prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions (8 g SSA and 6 g BSA per 100 mL distilled water). Plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 24 hours (ISO 6579-1:2017). Colonies suggestive of *S. Typhi* (black centers on SSA; metallic sheen on BSA) were sub-cultured on Nutrient Agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Pure isolates were stored in Amies transport media at –2°C for further analysis.

Biochemical and Serological Confirmation

Presumptive isolates were subjected to biochemical tests, including Triple Sugar Iron (TSI), urease, citrate utilization, methyl red, Voges-Proskauer, and motility assays, following the CLSI (2020) standards. Isolates consistent with *S. Typhi* were further confirmed using slide agglutination with Salmonella-specific polyvalent antisera (Wellcome Diagnostics, UK), according to the manufacturer's instructions.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST)

The Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method was used on Mueller-Hinton Agar (MHA), following the CLSI (2020 and 2023) guidelines. The antibiotic panel included ceftriaxone (30 µg), gentamicin (10 µg), cotrimoxazole (25 µg), levofloxacin (5 µg), netilmicin (30 µg), tetracycline (30 µg), amoxicillin/clavulanic acid (20/10 µg), and ofloxacin (5 µg) using standard disks (Himedia Combi 78 and G-I-Plus). Zone diameters were measured and interpreted based on the CLSI breakpoints for *Salmonella* species. MDR was defined as resistance to three or more antibiotic classes, including at least one beta-lactam, fluoroquinolone, and aminoglycoside or macrolide, consistent with international definitions (Magiorakos et al., 2012).

Sociodemographic and Clinical Data

Structured questionnaires were used to collect data on age, sex, residence (urban/semi-urban/rural), educational level, occupation, household water source, sanitation, recent hospitalization, prior antibiotic use, and self-medication behavior. These data were used to assess associations with phenotypic resistance patterns.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis

Retrospective data were descriptively analyzed to determine the proportion of annual resistance. Changes over time were summarized using trend plots and slope calculations. For prospective data, the prevalence and resistance rates were calculated using 95% confidence intervals. Bivariate associations were tested using the chi-square test. Logistic regression models were used to assess the predictors of MDR, adjusting for age, sex, and residence. Model diagnostics included the Hosmer-Lemeshow test and area under the ROC curve. Analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics Version 28.0 and R version 4.3.1.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Niger State Ministry of Health Ethics Committee (Reference: ERC PAN/2023/07/27). Written informed consent was obtained from all the participants. All data were anonymized to ensure confidentiality and compliance with ethical standards.

RESULTS

Temporal Trends in Antibiotic Resistance (2014–2023)

Retrospective analysis of *S. Typhi* isolates (2014–2023) showed a progressive increase in resistance to ciprofloxacin, azithromycin, gentamicin, and ampicillin (Figure 1). Ciprofloxacin resistance rose from 18% in 2014 to 36% in 2022, peaking at 37% in 2019. Azithromycin resistance fluctuated, increasing

from 12% in 2015 to 35% in 2023. Gentamicin resistance increased gradually from 2.5% in 2014 to 4.1% in 2023. Ampicillin resistance remained consistently high, with an average of 65% across the study period. Resistance to amoxicillin-clavulanate peaked at 51% in 2019 and remained above 30% through 2023. Erythromycin resistance varied widely, peaking at 48% in 2019. These trends indicate a shift toward reduced susceptibility across multiple classes of antibiotics.

Figure 1: Temporal trends in antibiotic resistance of *Salmonella* Typhi isolates in Niger State, Nigeria (2014–2023)

Gender and Age Distribution (2014–2023)

Males consistently accounted for a greater proportion of *S. Typhi* cases throughout the surveillance period, as shown in Figure 2. The age

group 21–40 years had the highest prevalence, followed by 0–20 years. Individuals aged ≥ 61 years showed the lowest case frequency across all years (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Gender distribution of *Salmonella* Typhi cases in Niger State from 2014 to 2023

Figure 3: Age distribution of *Salmonella* Typhi cases in Niger State (2014–2023)

Prospective Prevalence of *S. Typhi* (2023–2024)

Among the 624 individuals recruited in the prospective phase, 228 were confirmed to be positive for *S. Typhi*, yielding a prevalence of 36.5%. In total, 310 presumptive *Salmonella* isolates were obtained from stool samples and subjected to biochemical and serological tests. Of these, 228 (74%) exhibited biochemical characteristics of the *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhi. All underwent serological confirmation with *Salmonella* polyvalent antisera, with slide agglutination tests for O (somatic) and H

(flagellar) antigens yielding strong positive reactions. The highest prevalence occurred in the 18–27-year age group (83%), followed by the 28–37 year age group (11%). Males constituted 52.6% of the positive cases. The prevalence varied significantly by residential setting: semi-urban areas (45.5%), rural areas (30.1%), and urban areas (24.4%) ($p = 0.022$), as shown in Table 1. Wushishi (50%), Lapai (43.3%), and Sabon Wuse (40%) had the highest geographical prevalence (Figure 4).

Table 1: Community Prevalence of *Salmonella* Typhi in Niger State (2023–2024)

Parameter	Category	Participants (n)	S. Typhi positive cases (n)	Prevalence (%)	p-Value
Age	18–27	306	190	83	0.0001
	28–37	104	25	11	
	38–47	56	12	5	
	48–77	8	1	0	
Gender	Male	328	120	52.6	0.587
	Female	296	108	47.4	
Residence	Urban	152	56	24.4	0.022
	Rural	188	69	30.1	
	Semi-urban	284	103	45.5	

Figure 4: Geographic distribution of *Salmonella* Typhi prevalence across twelve communities in Niger State (2023–2024)**Phenotypic Antimicrobial Resistance Profiles (2023–2024)**

Of the 228 isolates, 173 (75.9%) were resistant to ≥ 3 antibiotics. Strict MDR, defined as resistance to one β -lactam, one fluoroquinolone, and one aminoglycoside or macrolide (Magiorakos et al., 2012), was observed in 13 (5.7 %) isolates. Broader co-resistance involving sulphonamides

and tetracyclines was identified in 23 isolates (10.1%).

Resistance to amoxicillin-clavulanate was universal (100%), followed by tetracycline (79.5%), cotrimoxazole (73.5%), and ceftriaxone (20.4%). High sensitivities were observed for netilmicin (86%) and levofloxacin (83.6%). Susceptibility profiles are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Antibiotic Susceptibility Profiles of *S. Typhi* Isolates (n = 228)

Antibiotic	Sensitive (%)	Intermediate (%)	Resistant (%)	p-value
Amoxicillin-Clavulanate (AMC)	0	0	100	0.001
Tetracycline (TE)	3.1	17.3	79.5	0.001
Cotrimoxazole (COT)	7.1	19.4	73.5	0.001
Ceftriaxone (CTR)	41.8	37.7	20.4	0.005
Gentamicin (GEN)	78.5	17.3	4.1	0.012
Levofloxacin (LE)	83.6	12.2	4.1	0.023
Netilmicin (NET)	86	12.2	2	0.018
Ofloxacin (OF)	82.6	13.2	4	0.001

Predictors of MDR-*Salmonella* Typhi Prevalence in Niger State

Logistic regression analysis identified recent hospitalization ($\beta = -7.40, p = 0.027$) and prior antibiotic use ($\beta = -0.07, p = 0.042$) as significant predictors of resistance. Self-medication ($\beta = -2.17, p = 0.058$) and frequent antibiotic use ($\beta = 0.03, p = 0.060$) approached significance. The model showed an acceptable fit (Hosmer–Lemeshow $p > 0.05$) and predictive power (AUC = 0.78).

DISCUSSION

This study presents a decade-long surveillance and contemporary cross-sectional assessment of phenotypic antimicrobial resistance in *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhi (*S. Typhi*) in Niger State, Nigeria. To the best of our knowledge, this is the most comprehensive regional dataset in West Africa linking temporal resistance trends with microbiologically confirmed prevalence, demographic risk factors, and antimicrobial exposure behaviors. The findings revealed a persistently high *S. Typhi* prevalence, widespread antibiotic resistance, notable demographic and geographic variations in disease burden, and emerging multidrug resistance (MDR) in a region facing infrastructural and regulatory constraints.

Retrospective resistance data from 2014 to 2023 revealed rising non-susceptibility to ciprofloxacin and azithromycin, two key agents currently used in typhoid therapy. Ciprofloxacin resistance peaked at 37% in 2019, whereas azithromycin resistance reached 35% by 2023, suggesting a growing therapeutic erosion. These findings mirror resistance trajectories documented in South Asia, where fluoroquinolone and macrolide overuse have driven the emergence of extensively drug-resistant (XDR) *S. Typhi* strains (Klemm et al., 2018; Tanmoy et al., 2024). In Nigeria, poor regulatory enforcement and high rates of over-the-counter access to antimicrobials likely accelerate this trend (Okeke et al., 2007; Akinyemi et al., 2022).

Amoxicillin-clavulanate resistance reached 100% in prospective isolates, indicating complete therapeutic failure of this commonly used beta-lactam combination. This finding is particularly alarming, surpassing the resistance rates reported in Pakistan's XDR outbreaks and signaling a potentially broader dissemination of

resistance genes such as *bla*TEM or *CTX-M*-type enzymes (Musa et al., 2020; Rasheed et al., 2020). Additionally, the cotrimoxazole resistance exceeded 70%, confirming the obsolescence of this once-standard treatment. These trends indicate a narrowing window of effective empirical therapy, with levofloxacin and netilmicin being the only agents that retained over 80% susceptibility. Nonetheless, their continued efficacy cannot be presumed without urgent containment of over-the-counter misuse and empirical prescription practices.

The longitudinal and prospective data provide compelling evidence of phenotypic resistance fixation to amoxicillin-clavulanate. During the 2014–2023 surveillance period, resistance to AMC exhibited episodic peaks, reaching 51% in 2019 before declining slightly. However, in the 2023–2024 cross-sectional phase, the resistance reached 100%, and no isolate demonstrated an intermediate or sensitive response. This finding suggests that AMC resistance has become entrenched within the local *S. Typhi* population, likely due to repeated exposure and selective pressure from empirical overuse in both public and private health care settings. Similar resistance saturation has been reported in South Asia, where amoxicillin-clavulanate resistance exceeded 90% among typhoidal *Salmonella*, coinciding with plasmid-mediated *bla*TEM and *bla*CTX-M gene circulation (Tanmoy et al., 2024). In contrast, studies from East Africa, such as Kariuki and Onsare (2024), have reported moderate AMC resistance (<40%) in urban Nairobi, indicating geographic heterogeneity in the evolution of resistance. The near-total resistance observed in Niger State reflects not only the therapeutic redundancy of AMC, but also highlights a critical policy failure in antibiotic regulations. This finding calls for immediate revision of empirical treatment guidelines, particularly in primary care centers where AMC remains a default prescription for febrile illness.

The resistance to a beta-lactam/beta-lactamase inhibitor combination such as AMC also raises concerns over possible co-selection for extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) phenotypes, which may undermine the utility of cephalosporins, a trend observed in Lagos and North-West Nigeria (Akinyemi et al., 2022; Moro et al., 2022). Although genotypic data were not included in this study, the phenotypic resistance

profile strongly suggested the emergence of *S. Typhi* lineages with plasmid-stabilized beta-lactamase expression. Future studies incorporating whole-genome sequencing (WGS) or targeted PCR are urgently required to confirm this hypothesis.

Prospective data showed a 36.5% *S. Typhi* prevalence in communities, with the highest burden in young adults (18–27 years) and semi-urban communities. These demographics align with previous global studies identifying adolescents and young adults as high-risk groups owing to increased exposure, mobility, and suboptimal sanitation (Crump et al., 2004; Marchello et al., 2019). The disproportionate burden in semi-urban areas suggests a “transitional infrastructure gap where partial WASH coverage fails to meet population needs. Areas such as Wushishi and Lapai recorded prevalence rates exceeding 40%, which may indicate localized environmental contamination or breakdown in municipal water safety. Similar trends have been documented in peri-urban zones in East and West Africa (Murphy et al., 2017).

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing of 228 isolates demonstrated a worrisome resistance landscape. All the isolates were resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanate. Over 70% of the patients showed resistance to cotrimoxazole and tetracycline, which are still in empirical use in many rural clinics. Levofloxacin and netilmicin retained >80% susceptibility, although their efficacy may be short lived without intervention. These patterns resemble those observed in Lagos, Kenya, and Lahore, where resistance has shifted from traditional first-line agents to more reliable alternatives (Akinoyemi et al., 2018; Rasheed et al., 2020; Kariuki and Onsare, 2024).

By the Magiorakos et al. (2012) definition, 5.7% of isolates qualified as MDR (resistant to one β -lactam, one fluoroquinolone, and one aminoglycoside or macrolide). However, 75.9% were resistant to at least three antibiotics, highlighting broader clinical challenges beyond the MDR label. The high frequency of multi-class resistance suggests a complex resistance burden, possibly involving horizontal gene transfer and plasmid-mediated mechanisms. This hypothesis is supported by regional reports of *bla*_{TEM}, *qnr*, and *aac*(3) gene carriage in *S. Typhi* (Musa et al., 2020; Yusof et al., 2022).

Predictive modeling revealed that recent hospitalization and prior antibiotic use were statistically significant risk factors for resistance, supporting the World Health Organization Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (WHO GLASS) surveillance findings on healthcare-associated AMR propagation (WHO, 2021). The near-significant role of self-medication highlights Nigeria’s widespread issue of antibiotic access without prescription, which contributes to resistance in both community and hospital settings (Okeke et al., 2007). Males showed a slightly higher prevalence than females, potentially reflecting occupational exposure and differential health-seeking behavior, consistent with patterns reported in Iraq and Southern Nigeria (Nassir et al., 2024; Nwosu et al., 2023).

Although phenotypic resistance data provide actionable insights, several limitations warrant discussion. First, the absence of genotypic testing in this study precludes the identification of specific resistance determinants or plasmid structures, which limits mechanistic interpretation. Second, seasonal patterns were not evaluated due to the study design, despite the known seasonality in typhoid transmission. Third, the rural representation in the prospective sample was limited by accessibility constraints, potentially underestimating the prevalence in remote communities. Nevertheless, the strengths of this study, including the use of a dual-phase design, rigorous microbiological confirmation, and linkage of clinical, behavioral, and geographic data, offer valuable contributions to typhoid control strategies. The high burden of resistance in semi-urban areas necessitates urgent investment in targeted WASH infrastructure and routine water quality surveillance. The continued use of ineffective empirical therapies such as cotrimoxazole and amoxicillin-clavulanate must be discontinued in favor of the updated local guidelines informed by real-time resistance data.

Finally, our findings support the immediate introduction of typhoid conjugate vaccines (TCVs) into Nigeria’s routine immunization schedule, especially for school-age and working-age populations. Without aggressive national action, combining the regulation of antibiotic use, diagnostics, and vaccination, the risk of

untreatable typhoids in West Africa may soon become a reality.

Conclusion

This study provides the first longitudinal phenotypic analysis of MDR *S. Typhi* in Niger State and reveals an evolving resistance landscape marked by widespread beta-lactam and sulfonamide resistance, a rising trend in fluoroquinolone and macrolide resistance, and a high MDR prevalence in semi-urban populations. The study underscores the necessity for immediate revision of antibiotic treatment protocols, scaling up of diagnostic infrastructure, and introduction of TCVs. Strengthening surveillance systems using molecular diagnostics is essential for tracking and curbing the spread of resistance. Without decisive policy and public health action, the risk of entering a post-treatment era of typhoid fever in West Africa remains unacceptably high.

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Conflict of Interest

None declared.

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